

Research Papers

Tailoring crystallization protocols to boost ionic conductivity in $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ solid electrolytes via controlled two-step thermal processing

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ABSTRACT

$\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ is considered one of the most promising sulfide-based solid electrolytes for all-solid-state lithium batteries (ASSLBs) however, its complex crystallization dynamics present challenges in achieving maximum ionic conductivity. In this work, a comprehensive thermal and kinetic study elucidates the crystallization behavior of amorphous $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$, focusing on how controlled nucleation and growth dynamics governs its structure–property relationships. Non-isothermal differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) combined with Kissinger, Ozawa, Matsuda, and local activation energy models reveals crystallization activation barriers ($E_a \approx 230\text{--}280 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), highlighting a thermally activated, multi-stage transformation mechanism. A two-step heat treatment protocol, consisting of nucleation at 180°C for 30 min followed by crystallization at 250°C , substantially improves structural coherence and microstructural homogeneity. This kinetic tailoring leads to superior electrochemical performance, with room-temperature ionic conductivity reaching $1.98 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ and a Li^+ diffusion activation energy barrier of 0.25 eV . Structural and morphological analyses performed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) confirm that controlled nucleation promotes uniform crystallite formation. These findings demonstrate that nucleation engineering is an effective strategy for enhancing crystallization pathways and unlocking the full potential of $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ and related glass–ceramic electrolytes in next-generation ASSLBs.

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1. Introduction

The growing demand for high-energy-density, long-life, and inherently safe energy storage systems has intensified research into all-solid-state lithium batteries (ASSLBs). By replacing flammable liquid electrolytes with solid-state counterparts, ASSLBs offer enhanced safety, superior thermal stability, and higher volumetric energy density. Among the various solid electrolytes, sulfide-based materials have attracted particular attention due to their high lithium-ion conductivities ($10^{-3}\text{--}10^{-2} \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$), favorable mechanical deformability, and relatively low crystallization temperatures compared to oxide-based electrolytes

[1–4].

One of the most promising members of the sulfide electrolyte family is $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$, a metastable glass–ceramic phase formed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{S}\text{--}\text{P}_2\text{S}_5$ system. It exhibits room-temperature ionic conductivities exceeding $1 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ and can be synthesized via mechanochemical ball milling followed by crystallization heat treatment (typically below 300°C) [5,6]. Its crystal structure comprises PS_4^{3-} and $\text{P}_2\text{S}_7^{4-}$ polyhedral units that form interconnected lithium-ion pathways, enabling fast ion transport. The high ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ is strongly dependent on its thermal processing conditions, particularly the crystallization protocol. Improper crystallization treatments can lead to undesirable phase separation (e.g., $\text{Li}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_6$, Li_3PS_4), excessive grain growth, or the presence of residual amorphous regions that limit Li^+ transport [7–9].

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Although $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ has been widely recognized for its high lithium-ion conductivity ($0.6\text{--}1.3\text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$), significant discrepancies persist in reported values depending on synthesis and heat-treatment protocols [10,11]. These variations can be primarily attributed to insufficient control over nucleation and growth processes during synthesis and subsequent heat-treatment steps. Unlike in oxide-based glass-ceramics, where nucleation engineering is a well-established strategy, its systematic implementation in sulfide electrolytes remains limited [7,12–14]. In particular, critical questions remain concerning the influence of the heat-treatment pathway on nucleation density, crystallite size, and microstructural evolution. Therefore, the systematic application of stepwise thermal treatment and kinetic analysis for optimizing sulfide-based solid electrolytes remain an area of active and important research [8,15–17]. Research on sulfide-based solid electrolytes by different groups has revealed that a two-step heat-treatment procedure has a pronounced impact on ionic conductivity [7] [18]. Although these reports have largely identified empirical conditions for improving conductivity, a comprehensive kinetic mapping of nucleation rates, growth rates, and their explicit correlation to ionic conductivity remains underexplored.

To better understand crystallization mechanisms, kinetic models including Kissinger, Ozawa, Matusita, Augis–Bennett, and Avrami provide insights into activation energy (E_a), Avrami exponent (n), and growth dimensionality. These models are particularly effective for assessing complex nucleation and growth behaviors under non-isothermal conditions [19–21]. Notably, methods such as local activation energy analysis and the Ray–Day approach have been employed to decouple early-stage nucleation from subsequent crystal growth, particularly in multistep heat treatments.

Another often-overlooked factor is the homogeneity of the amorphous precursor obtained from mechanochemical synthesis. Small variations in milling protocols can lead to different local stoichiometries and structural heterogeneities, which subsequently influence crystallization behavior. Our recent work [22] established a reproducible route to obtain highly homogeneous amorphous $\text{Li}_2\text{S}\text{--}\text{P}_2\text{S}_5$ precursors, thereby decoupling precursor variability from thermal effects and allowing a more precise assessment of crystallization kinetics.

In this work, we build upon these foundations to quantitatively dissect the crystallization kinetics of $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ prepared via mechanochemical synthesis. By combining non-isothermal DSC with classical kinetic models and Ray–Day analysis, we map nucleation and growth behavior in detail. Single-step and two-step heat treatments are systematically compared based on the crystallinity, morphology, band gap, and ionic conductivity evaluated through XRD, FESEM, UV–vis, and EIS. Importantly, our results demonstrate that a two-step protocol ($180\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ pre-nucleation $\rightarrow 250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ crystallization) yields enhanced crystallinity, improved microstructural homogeneity, and a twofold increase in conductivity (to $1.98\text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$). These findings establish controlled nucleation engineering as a robust pathway for tailoring $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$, while also refining the scientific framework connecting crystallization kinetics to electrochemical properties in sulfide-based glass–ceramic electrolytes.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Materials and synthesis of amorphous $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$

The $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ precursor was synthesized via a mechanochemical route using high-purity lithium sulfide (Li_2S , 99.9%, Alfa Aesar) and phosphorus pentasulfide (P_2S_5 , 99%, Sigma-Aldrich). All precursors were handled exclusively in an argon-filled glovebox (MBraun, H_2O and $\text{O}_2 < 1\text{ ppm}$) to avoid hydrolysis and oxidation. A stoichiometric molar ratio of 7:3 ($\text{Li}_2\text{S}:\text{P}_2\text{S}_5$) corresponding to the $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ composition was used. Based on our previous study, we performed a brief hand-milling step with an agate mortar and pestle before the main planetary milling to ensure the precursors were well-mixed [22]. After that, the powders were charged into an 80 mL zirconia milling jar containing ten

10 mm zirconia balls, maintaining a ball-to-powder weight ratio of 20:1. Milling was performed using a planetary mill (Fritsch Pulverisette 7 Premium Line) at 400 rpm for 40 h, with 15-min pauses after every 60 min to prevent overheating and promote uniform mixing. After milling, a pale yellowish amorphous powder was obtained and stored under an argon atmosphere for further processing.

2.2. Thermal treatment procedures

Two distinct thermal treatment protocols were employed to study crystallization behavior and ionic conductivity:

- (i) Single-step thermal treatment: The amorphous powders were sealed into quartz ampoules under argon atmosphere and heated at fixed temperatures of $240\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 260 and $270\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h using a programmable muffle furnace. These temperatures were selected based on the crystallization onset and peak temperatures obtained from DSC analysis.
- (ii) Two-step thermal treatment: The amorphous powders were first heated to $180\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and held for 30 min (nucleation stage), followed by heating to $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h (crystallization stage). Both steps were performed sequentially without intermediate cooling. This approach aimed to enhance nucleation while minimizing undesired secondary phase formation. Unless otherwise noted, a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ was used in all thermal treatments.

2.3. Structural and thermal characterization

Phase analysis and crystallite size were evaluated via X-ray diffraction (Rigaku D/MAX 2200, Cu $K\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 1.5406\text{ \AA}$). Patterns were collected in the 2θ range of $10^\circ\text{--}60^\circ$ at a scan rate of $1^\circ/\text{min}$. Crystallite size (D) was calculated using the Scherrer eq. (1):

$$D = \frac{K \lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \quad (1)$$

where $K = 0.9$ is the shape factor, λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM), and θ is the Bragg angle.

Thermal behavior and crystallization kinetics were investigated by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter). 6 mg of powder was sealed in aluminum crucibles and heated under argon flow ($40\text{ mL}/\text{min}$) from room temperature to $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Heating rates of 3, 5, 10, 15, 20, and $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ were used for non-isothermal kinetic modeling via Kissinger, Ozawa, and Matusita equations. Isothermal DSC was also conducted at selected nucleation temperatures ($170\text{--}210\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) to optimize pre-crystallization conditions.

For quantitative nucleation analysis, the Ray and Day model was employed using custom-designed thermal cycles. The crystal growth rate (U) was extracted from crystallite sizes (XRD) obtained after varying heating durations ($5\text{--}180\text{ min}$ at $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Nucleation rate (I) and initial nucleus density (N_q) were calculated based on DSC peak areas and the corresponding temperature–time profiles.

Morphological changes resulting from thermal treatment were examined using field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, Quanta FEG 450). Optical band gap energies were derived from UV–Vis diffuse reflectance spectra (Shimadzu UV-1900i). The optical bandgap (E_g) was determined using the Tauc relation: $(\alpha h\nu)^2 = A(h\nu - E_g)$, where α is the absorption coefficient, h is Planck's constant, and ν is the frequency. By plotting $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus photon energy ($h\nu$) and extrapolating the linear region to the x-axis, the direct band gap values were obtained. Samples were dispersed in anhydrous n-hexane to avoid surface oxidation during measurement.

2.4. Electrochemical characterization

Ionic conductivities were measured at room temperature by elec-

trochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS, Gamry REF1000) technique. Pellets were fabricated by uniaxially pressing ~ 100 mg of powder (diameter = 10 mm, thickness ≈ 0.85 mm) at 300 MPa using a stainless-steel die. Stainless steel disks were used as lithium-ion blocking electrodes, and the assembly was sealed in a custom Swagelok-type cell under inert atmosphere. Impedance spectra were collected in the frequency range of 1 MHz to 0.1 Hz with a perturbation voltage of 10 mV. Nyquist plots were used to extract bulk resistance values, which were then used to calculate ionic conductivity (σ) using the formula (2):

$$\sigma = \frac{L}{RA} \quad (2)$$

where L is the pellet thickness, R is the resistance, and A is the pellet surface area.

For selected samples (250 °C single-step and 180 °C + 260 °C two-step), temperature-dependent EIS measurements were conducted between 25 and 80 °C. The activation energy for ionic conduction was extracted from the Arrhenius eq. (3):

$$\sigma(T) = \sigma_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{kT}\right) \quad (3)$$

where E_a is the activation energy, k is the Boltzmann constant and T is absolute temperature.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1(a) presents X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns after 20, 30, and 40 h of milling. While the 20-h sample exhibits distinct residual diffraction peaks corresponding to unreacted Li_2S and P_2S_5 phases, these reflections diminish significantly after 30 h of milling. After 40 h of milling, the diffraction pattern transforms into two broad amorphous halos centered at approximately $2\theta \approx 15^\circ$ and 30° , confirming the formation of a fully amorphous sulfide matrix. This result is consistent with previous reports demonstrating that prolonged mechanochemical activation promotes the formation of a glassy sulfide matrix [6,23].

Fig. 1(b) displays the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) thermogram of the amorphous $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ powder. A pronounced exothermic peak emerges between 240 °C and 265 °C, with a maximum at 252 °C,

indicating the crystallization window. This peak is attributed to the structural reordering of PS_4^{3-} and $\text{P}_2\text{S}_7^{4-}$ polyhedral units within the amorphous matrix. Two exothermic features near 290 °C and 320 °C suggest thermal degradation or transformation into less conductive byproducts such as $\text{Li}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_6$, as observed in previous studies on overheated sulfide glass-ceramics [24,25]. Therefore, maintaining the crystallization temperature below ~ 290 °C is essential to avoid the formation of electrochemically unfavorable phases.

To determine the onset temperature of crystallization, amorphous samples were pre-heated at 170, 180, 190, 200, and 210 °C for 1 h, followed by XRD analysis (Fig. 1c). No distinct diffraction peaks were detected at 170 °C and 180 °C, indicating the absence of long-range crystalline order detectable by XRD. However, considering the detection limit of XRD for nanometer-scale domains, this temperature range is more appropriately described as a nucleation-dominated regime, where thermally activated sub-critical or XRD-silent nuclei may form without the development of fully grown crystallites. Therefore, the lack of observable diffraction peaks at 170–180 °C does not preclude the presence of early-stage nuclei. Instead, it suggests that crystallization is kinetically suppressed while nucleation processes dominate, consistent with the subsequent enhancement of crystallization observed upon heating above ~ 190 °C. However, at 190 °C, weak diffraction peaks corresponding to $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ (ICSD No. 157654) emerged, increasing in intensity at 200 °C and 210 °C. These observations suggest that XRD observable crystallization initiates at ~ 190 °C, while maintaining substantial amorphousness. Thus, the 170–190 °C range is deemed ideal for controlled nucleation, inducing stable nucleus formation without triggering significant crystal growth.

Pre-nucleation below the crystallization temperature is known to enhance the number of nucleation sites for the desired phase, whereas heat treatment without pre-nucleation at or above the crystallization peak (e.g., 252 °C) can result in uncontrolled grain growth and phase inhomogeneity [12,26]. Based on this concept, a two-step crystallization strategy namely (i) nucleation at 180–200 °C to increase nucleus density, and (ii) crystallization at 240–260 °C to achieve full phase formation without degradation was adopted. This approach, consistent with classical nucleation-growth separation theory, enables better control over microstructure and ionic transport properties, as further detailed in

Fig. 1. (a) XRD patterns of the samples subjected to ball-milling for different time intervals, (b) DSC thermogram of the amorphous powders, (c) XRD analyses of the amorphous powders heat treated at different temperatures for one hour.

the following sections.

To optimize nucleation conditions, a systematic approach combining isothermal heat treatment and DSC analysis was applied to extract quantitative kinetic parameters, including nucleation rate (I), crystal growth rate (U), and initial nuclei density (N_q), using the Ray and Day model.

Fig. 2a illustrates the influence of short isothermal holds (10 min) at temperatures between 160 and 210 °C on subsequent crystallization behavior. Unlike Fig. 1c, which used a prolonged 60-min hold to rule out crystal growth, Fig. 2a focuses on the rapid formation of nuclei. Each pre-treated sample was rapidly quenched after the isothermal hold to suppress further transformations and then subjected to thermal analysis. The observed crystallization peak heights, normalized by sample mass, serve as indicators of the nucleation extent during pre-treatment. The highest crystallization peak appeared at 180 °C, closely followed by 190 °C, signifying that these temperatures induce a high density of stable nuclei. Above 190 °C, the reduction in peak height likely results from the onset of crystal growth overlapping with nucleation, which limits the distinction and control over the nucleation stage [7,24].

To identify the optimum time interval for nucleation at 180 °C, holding times of from 10 to 60 min at 10 min intervals were evaluated (Fig. 2b). The DSC peak height reached its maximum after a 30-min hold, suggesting the optimum nucleation site density. Shorter holding times resulted in insufficient nuclei, while extended holds beyond 40 min likely induced Ostwald ripening, wherein larger nuclei grow at the expense of smaller ones, reducing overall nucleation density and homogeneity [6,27,28]. These results indicate that a 30-min hold at 180 °C induces a dense, homogeneous distribution of nuclei favorable for subsequent crystal growth.

For quantitative analysis of nucleation and growth, the Ray and Day model was employed using controlled thermal profiles (Fig. 2c). In the thermal profile shown in Fig. 2c-1, amorphous powders were directly heated to 250 °C and held for 5–10 min to isolate the crystal growth

stage without prior nucleation. In comparison, the profile in Fig. 2c-2 incorporated a pre-nucleation step at 180 °C for 30 min before applying the same high-temperature treatment. The difference in crystallization peak areas between these paths allowed calculation of the nucleation rate (I) using the Ray and Day eq. (4):

$$It_N + N_q = \frac{3(A_1m_2 - A_2m_1)}{\pi U^3 (A_1m_2t_{G2}^3 - A_2m_1t_{G1}^3)} \quad (4)$$

where t_N is the nucleation time, A_1 and A_2 are DSC peak areas, m_1 and m_2 are sample masses, and U is the growth rate.

The growth rate U was determined via isothermal XRD at 250 °C, where crystallite size increased linearly with time. Applying the Scherrer equation, a growth rate of 0.0461 nm/min was calculated (Fig. S1). Substituting this value into the Ray and Day model yielded a nuclei density of $N_q = 1.61 \times 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-3}$.

Using the thermal paths depicted in Fig. 2c, the nucleation rate I was computed from DSC measurements of samples subjected to both nucleation and growth. In this protocol, amorphous $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ was first held at 180 °C for 30 min to initiate nucleation. This was followed by cooling to 50 °C to freeze the structure, and subsequently reheating to 250 °C for 5 or 10 min for crystal growth. A subsequent DSC scan at a constant heating rate of 10 °C/min up to 300 °C was conducted to measure the remaining crystallization enthalpy. This sequential heating and cooling approach ensured temporal separation of nucleation and growth, a critical condition for the Ray and Day model [29].

Fig. 2d shows that the DSC peak area decreased significantly as the growth time increased from 5 to 10 min, indicating that more nuclei had crystallized during the longer hold, leaving fewer residual sites. Based on the sequential heating-cooling protocol and Ray-Day modeling, the nucleation rate was calculated to be $I = 1.92 \times 10^{25} \text{ min}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$. This value is consistent with the results obtained in Fig. 2a, where the crystallization peak was maximized at 180 °C following a 30-min hold,

Fig. 2. (a) DSC peak height after short nucleation at 160–210 °C, (b) Effect of holding at 180 °C for nucleation on DSC peak height, (c) Thermal profiles for kinetic analysis, (d) DSC peak areas after 250 °C growth.

further supporting the selection of this temperature as the optimum for achieving a high nucleation rate.

To further elucidate the crystallization mechanism of amorphous $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ and to evaluate the energy barriers associated with the phase transformation, non-isothermal DSC measurements were carried out at various heating rates (3, 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 °C/min). As shown in Fig. 3a, the exothermic crystallization peak systematically shifted to higher temperatures with increasing heating rate. The shift in the peaks arises from the reduced time available for nucleation and growth at higher heating rates, therefore necessitating elevated temperatures to initiate the phase transformation as of typical for glass–ceramic materials and confirms the non-isothermal nature of $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ crystallization [7,21,30]. This kinetic behavior provides a foundation for applying classical models such as Kissinger, Ozawa, and Matusita to extract activation (E_a) energies and growth parameters.

The crystallization activation energy (E_a) was determined using two classical non-isothermal models: Kissinger and Ozawa. Both approaches relate the shift in peak crystallization temperature (T_p) with the applied heating rate (β). The Kissinger eq. (5) is expressed as:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T_p^2}\right) = -\frac{E_a}{RT_p} + \text{const} \quad (5)$$

where β is the heating rate, T_p is the peak crystallization temperature, R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol·K), and E_a is the activation energy. From the linear fitting of $\ln(\beta/T_p^2)$ (Fig. 3b, left axis) versus $1/T_p$, the activation energy was calculated as 269.62 ± 10.97 kJ/mol. Similarly, the Ozawa equation is given as (6):

$$\ln(\beta) = -\frac{E_a}{RT_p} + \text{const} \quad (6)$$

A linear plot of $\ln(\beta)$ versus $1/T_p$ similarly gives E_a from the slope. Eq. (6) was applied, yielding an activation energy of 278.35 ± 10.98 kJ/mol. The consistency between the Kissinger and Ozawa models validates the reliability of the thermal data and indicates a relatively high crystallization energy barrier for $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$, in line with values reported for other complex sulfide-based systems such as $\text{Li}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_6$ and Li_3PS_4 [18,29,31].

To better characterize the crystallization, the Avrami exponent (n) was extracted using the Augis–Bennett approximation, which provides insight into nucleation dynamics and growth dimensionality. Using the Augis–Bennett approximation, which relates the transformation fraction

χ and heating rate β (Eq. 7), the evolution of Avrami exponent (n) was calculated at different temperatures.

$$\ln[-\ln(1-\chi)] = -n\ln\beta + \text{const} \quad (7)$$

The approach enables isoconversional analysis by plotting $\ln[-\ln(1-\chi)]$ against $\ln\beta$ at constant degrees of crystallization (χ) in which the χ was determined from the normalized area under the DSC exothermic peaks. As shown in Fig. 3c, Avrami exponent (n) values were calculated as 4.19 ± 0.3 at 245 °C, 4.95 ± 0.9 at 250 °C, and 4.87 ± 0.2 at 255 °C. Such high values indicate a three-dimensional interface-controlled growth mechanism, suggesting the presence of both continuous nucleation and anisotropic growth fronts in which the behavior is typical of complex glass–ceramic systems where crystallization occurs through bulk transformation rather than surface-limited processes [7,18,32,33].

To further deepen the analysis, the Matusita model, which is particularly suited for analysing non-isothermal crystallization under diffusion-controlled conditions, was applied. In addition to the Kissinger and Ozawa methods, it takes both nucleation and growth processes into account. The Matusita eq. (8) is given by:

$$\ln[-\ln(1-\chi)] = -n\ln(\beta) - \frac{1.052 m E_a}{RT} + \text{const} \quad (8)$$

here, χ represents the relative crystallinity, β is the heating rate, and m is the dimensionality of crystal growth, taken as $n = m + 1$ for bulk growth systems. Using Eq. (8) and isoconversional plots (Fig. 3d), an average activation energy of 267.98 ± 20.43 kJ/mol was calculated. The consistency across these independent methods supports the robustness of the derived kinetic parameters and highlights the diffusion-limited nature of $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ crystallization [34].

While the above models provide average E_a values over the entire crystallization range, they do not capture the energy variations throughout the transformation. Therefore, the local activation energy (E_a, χ) was calculated by Ozawa-based expression (Eq. 9) as a function of crystallization fraction (χ) using:

$$\ln(\beta) = -\frac{1.0516 E_{a\chi}}{RT} + \text{const} \quad (9)$$

Plots of $\ln(\beta)$ versus $-1051.6/RT$ (Fig. 3e) were generated at crystallization fractions from 0.1 to 0.9 (Fig. 3f). The results show a gradual decline in activation energy from 274.09 ± 8.46 kJ/mol at $\chi = 0.1$ to 245.48 ± 20.32 kJ/mol at $\chi = 0.9$. This trend indicates that early-stage crystallization requires a higher energy input, which is attributed to the

Fig. 3. (a) DSC curves at different heating rates, (b) Kissinger and Ozawa plots for E_a , (c) Avrami plots at selected temperatures, (d) Matusita kinetic analysis, (e-f) Local activation energy versus crystallization fraction.

energy barrier associated with nucleation. In contrast, the later stages of crystallization, dominated by growth on pre-formed nuclei, proceed with lower energy demands. Such a pattern is characteristic of multi-stage crystallization systems, where nucleation and growth are temporally and energetically distinct.

To isolate the kinetic effects of nucleation, a second set of DSC measurements was conducted on pre-nucleated samples. Samples were initially held at 180 °C for 30 min, the optimum nucleation condition identified previously, then subjected to DSC scans at varying heating rates (Fig. 4a). This pre-treatment decouples nucleation from growth, enabling a clear analysis of crystallization kinetics during the growth stage.

Using the Kissinger and Ozawa models on the DSC data of pre-nucleated samples, activation energies of 251.49 ± 8.56 kJ/mol and 259.14 ± 14.29 kJ/mol, respectively, were obtained (Fig. 4b). These values, slightly lower than those measured from fully amorphous samples, reflect the suppression of the nucleation barrier due to the prior thermal treatment. This confirms that once nuclei are established, the subsequent crystallization progresses with lower energetic demand, consistent with the expected reduction in activation barrier for the growth-dominated stage.

To further understand the growth dynamics, the Avrami exponent (n) was calculated under the same conditions (Fig. 4c). The n values remained high: 4.85 ± 0.6 at 245 °C, 4.59 ± 0.2 at 250 °C, 4.32 ± 0.2 at 255 °C, and 3.05 ± 0.5 at 260 °C indicating that three-dimensional interface-controlled growth continues to dominate even after nucleation. The slight decrease in n at higher temperatures may indicate the onset of grain coarsening or a transition toward diffusion-controlled growth, which is consistent with prolonged thermal exposure in glass-ceramic systems [35–37].

The Matusita model, when applied to pre-nucleated samples (Fig. 4d), produced an average activation energy of 255.81 ± 18.26 kJ/mol, consistent with a reduction in kinetic resistance due to pre-established nuclei. Compared to fully amorphous samples, the lower E_a reflects the enhanced crystallization kinetics facilitated by prior thermal structuring and increased lattice ordering.

The local activation energy profile of pre-nucleated samples (Fig. 4e–f) shows a progressive decrease in E_a from 229.41 ± 5.62 kJ/mol at $\chi = 0.1$ to 201.65 ± 10.36 kJ/mol at $\chi = 0.9$. This trend is indicative of a multi-stage crystallization process, where the initial transformation is energetically demanding due to lattice reorganization and defect migration, but the subsequent growth proceeds more easily

once a crystalline framework is established. This energy profile supports the concept of a multi-stage crystallization process, wherein nucleation and growth are temporally and energetically decoupled [24,38,39].

The summarized results in Table 1 clearly show that pre-nucleation at 180 °C for 30 min reduces the energy required for subsequent crystallization and stabilizes the growth mechanism. The decoupling of nucleation and growth results in more uniform grain structures and improved control over crystallite dimensions, which are essential for minimizing structural inhomogeneity in sulfide electrolytes. The correlation between reduced activation energy and enhanced ionic conductivity (Fig. 6) confirms the critical role of thermal history in tuning both structural and electrochemical properties [24,40,41].

The results confirm that controlling nucleation conditions offers a

Table 1
Comparative crystallization kinetic parameters for amorphous and pre-nucleated $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ samples, derived from various thermal analysis models.

Kinetic Model	Sample Type	Activation Energy (E_a , kJ/mol)	Notes
Kissinger	Amorphous	269.62 ± 10.97	Captures total nucleation and growth
	Pre-nucleated	251.49 ± 8.56	Reduced E_a reflects suppressed nucleation barrier
Ozawa	Amorphous	278.35 ± 10.98	Consistent with Kissinger; crystallized volume fraction not required
	Pre-nucleated	259.14 ± 14.29	Suggests reduced kinetic barrier after nucleation
Matusita	Amorphous	267.98 ± 20.43	Accounts for dimensional growth and interface effects
	Pre-nucleated	255.81 ± 18.26	Reflects enhanced phase alignment and growth efficiency
Local E_a ($\chi = 0.1-0.9$)	Amorphous	$274.09 \pm 8.46 \rightarrow 245.48 \pm 20.32$	Higher energy required at early stages due to nucleation
	Pre-nucleated	$229.41 \pm 5.62 \rightarrow 201.65 \pm 10.36$	Lower energy throughout growth due to pre-existing nuclei
Avrami Exponent (n)	Amorphous	4.19–4.95	Indicates 3D nucleation and interface-controlled growth
	Pre-nucleated	4.85 \rightarrow 3.05	Sustained 3D growth; slight reduction at higher T due to coarsening

Fig. 4. Crystallization kinetics of pre-nucleated $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ evaluated by (a) DSC at different heating rates, (b–c) modeled via Kissinger and Ozawa, (c) Avrami plots (d) Matusita plot (e–f) local activation energy methods.

reproducible method to influence crystallization kinetics in $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$. This approach also helps mitigate secondary phase formation that could otherwise hinder electrochemical performance [42].

Fig. 5 presents the structural, optical, and morphological characterizations performed on amorphous, single-step, and two-step crystallized $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ samples to validate the kinetic observations and assess the influence of thermal history on material properties critical for solid-state battery performance.

As shown in Fig. 5a, both the single-step and two-step annealed samples exhibit sharp XRD peaks corresponding to the $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ phase. Quantitatively, the two-step sample shows a slight increase of $\sim 1.12\%$ in the integrated intensity of the major diffraction peaks compared to the single-step sample. The crystallite sizes calculated using the Scherrer equation were determined to be 27.4 nm for the single-step process and 28.1 nm for the two-step process. Coupled with the Nyquist plots (Fig. 6a), the similarity in crystallite sizes possibly suggests that the conductivity difference arising from the two-step heat treatment is associated not with intragrain impedance but rather with the coherent structure of the grain boundaries, which results in a lower grain boundary impedance, and hence lower total impedance.

To investigate the effect of crystallization temperature, and the corresponding crystallite size, on the electronic structure, the optical band gap (E_g) was estimated by Tauc plots derived from UV-Vis absorption spectra (Fig. 5b). The E_g values showed a consistent decrease, from 5.02 eV in the amorphous state to 3.36 eV in the single-step crystallized sample, and further down to 3.13 eV in the two-step crystallized sample. This progressive narrowing of the band gap likely reflects improved long-range structural order associated with the increased crystallite sizes [43–45]. FESEM images in Fig. 5d reveal that the single-step sample exhibits irregularly shaped, inhomogeneous grains with partial agglomeration (grain sizes 500 nm–4 μm), suggesting non-uniform crystallization. In contrast, the two-step-treated powder (Fig. 5e) shows a significantly more uniform microstructure. The grain sizes (900 nm–1.8 μm) indicate that controlled nucleation limits excessive grain growth while promoting structural homogeneity. Although the observed particle sizes exceed the crystallite sizes derived

from XRD (~ 28 nm), this disparity reflects grain clustering rather than individual crystallite dimensions.

Overall, these results confirm that the two-step thermal treatment enhances not only the crystallographic ordering but also optimizes the electronic and morphological properties of $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$. All of which directly contribute to enhanced ionic conductivity in all-solid-state battery architectures [46,47].

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was employed to evaluate the impact of thermal treatment protocol on ionic conductivity. Nyquist plots (Fig. 6a) reveal semicircular responses in the high-frequency region followed by a tail at low frequency, characteristic of the total resistance comprising contributions from the bulk, grain boundary, electrode interfacial resistances. The two-step crystallized $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ exhibits a room-temperature ionic conductivity of $1.98 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, which is comparable to or higher than many previously reported values for $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ electrolytes prepared via conventional single-step heat treatments (typically $0.6\text{--}1.3 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) [10,11]. This improvement is achieved without increasing the crystallization temperature, underscoring the effectiveness of controlled nucleation in enhancing ionic transport. The Arrhenius plots (Fig. 6b) further substantiate this improvement. The activation energy (E_a) for lithium-ion transport, extracted from the slope of the linear $\ln \sigma$ vs. $1/T$ fit, decreased from 0.34 eV in the single-step sample to 0.25 eV following the two-step thermal protocol. This improvement in ionic conductivity and activation energy is likely due to the reduced grain boundary resistance facilitated by the optimized microstructure resulting from the two-stage heat treatment [44], [48–50]. To clearly illustrate the property enhancements enabled by controlled crystallization, Table 2 summarizes the crystallite size, optical band gap, room-temperature ionic conductivity, and activation energy values for both processing methods.

This comparative analysis reinforces that a two-step thermal protocol, involving a dedicated nucleation stage, significantly improves both the structural and electrochemical performance of $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$. Improved crystallinity, optimized grain morphology, and lower activation energy collectively contribute to enhanced ionic conductivity.

Fig. 5. (a) XRD patterns of single-step (heated to 250 °C, held 1 h) and two-step (heated to 180 °C, held 30 min; then to 250 °C, held 1 h) crystallized $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$, (b) UV-Vis derived optical band gaps, FESEM images showing morphological evolution of (c) amorphous, (d) single, and (e) two-step heat-treated samples.

Fig. 6. (a) Nyquist plots from EIS measurements of single and two-step crystallized $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$, (b) Arrhenius plots of temperature-dependent ionic conductivity and corresponding activation energy barriers for lithium diffusion.

Table 2

Comparative summary of structural and electrochemical properties for $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ processed via single and two-step crystallization strategies.

Treatment Protocol	Crystallite Size (nm)	Band Gap (eV)	Ionic Conductivity (S/cm at 25 °C)	Activation Energy E_a (eV)
Single-Step (250 °C, 2 h)	27.4	3.36	8.47×10^{-4}	0.34
Two-Step (180 °C 30 min + 250 °C 1 h)	28.1	3.13	1.98×10^{-3}	0.25

4. Conclusion

This study systematically investigated the crystallization kinetics and electrochemical behavior of amorphous $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ via thermal analysis, kinetic modeling, and microstructural characterization. Thermal analysis results revealed a complex crystallization behavior governed by crystallization activation energies (230–280 kJ/mol), and the Avrami exponent of $n \approx 4.2$ suggests three-dimensional bulk growth mechanisms. Importantly, pre-nucleation significantly reduced the energy barrier for subsequent crystallization, with activation energy values decreasing by ~ 30 kJ/mol. A two-step heat treatment protocol—comprising nucleation at 180 °C for 30 min followed by crystallization at 250 °C—was shown to enhance nucleation density. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy demonstrated that the optimized thermal route dramatically enhanced ionic conductivity (up to $1.98 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) while lowering the activation energy for Li^+ transport to 0.25 eV. Complementary XRD and FESEM analyses confirmed, respectively, sharper diffraction peaks and a more uniform grain morphology in the samples subjected to successive heat treatments for crystallization. A slight narrowing of the optical bandgap (from 3.36 eV to 3.13 eV) further indicated improved structural ordering. The results underscore the significance of decoupling nucleation and growth processes to tune the structural and functional properties of sulfide-based glass-ceramic electrolytes. These findings demonstrate that decoupling nucleation and growth via controlled thermal processing is a powerful strategy to tailor the structure-property relationships in sulfide-based glass-ceramic electrolytes. The presented methodology can be generalized for optimizing metastable solid electrolytes in next-generation all-solid-state lithium batteries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mustafa Celik: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology,

Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Abdulkadir Kızılaslan:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Akira Miura:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Kiyoharu Tadanaga:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Hatem Akbulut:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Tugrul Cetinkaya:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2026.121046>.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in [Zenodo] at doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17549302> [51].

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